

The Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center

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research institute affiliated with
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NERSC Technical Report no. 392

NANSAT SPRINT SUMMARY

SPRINT ENDING 2018-01-26

by

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REPORT

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Table of Content

Table of Content..... ii

Context..... 1

Team Members..... 1

Metrics 2

 Burn Down 2

 Stacked Burn Down 3

 Cumulative Flow..... 4

Contents and Assessment 4

 Sprint Planning..... 6

 Sprint Review..... 7

 Sprint Retrospective 7

 Other 7

Context

First Day of Sprint: 2018-01-09
Last Day of Sprint: 2018-01-26
Working Days in Sprint: 13.5
Sprint Goal: “Modernize and improve visibility and competitiveness of Nansat.”

Team Members

The following people participated in the sprint. Also listed are their roles, the days they were expected to work and the number of days they did work.

Name	Role	Planned Days	Worked Days
Hansen, Morten	Product Owner, Developer	13.5	10.5
Korosov, Anton	Developer	11.5	14.5
Moiseev, Artem	Developer	13.5	13.5
Park, Jeong-Won	Developer	13.5	13.5
Vines, Aleksander	Scrum Master, Developer	11	10.5

Metrics

Burn Down

The Burn Down chart displays number of points left on tasks that are not yet completed. The two slightly greyed out areas represent weekends, where no work was done. Note that on January 17 and 18 we adjusted the number of story points on two cards as it turned out they were more complex than previously estimated.

In the future we should fill in hours on each individual task and improve the time monitoring. This would result in a much nicer burndown chart based on # hours instead of points.

Stacked Burn Down

The stacked burndown chart displays the status of all tasks. The black area represents tasks that are not started. The blue area represents tasks that are in progress. The green area represents tasks that are completed.

Cumulative Flow

This chart gives a more detailed daily overview of the status of all the cards. The time range starts on January 9 to include everything from the beginning of the Planning meeting, which spanned over two days. Note that this is not a “Burn Down” but rather “Burn Up”.

Contents and Assessment

Total number of cards in backlog:	62
Number of cards selected for the sprint:	23
Number of cards completed:	14
Points selected for the sprint:	317
Points completed:	225

Story	Points	Result
Integration with Python Index (PyPi)	13	Finished
Increase test coverage	13	Finished
Docstring of VRT.get_projection() is wrong	1	Finished
Provide version for Python3	3	Finished
Errors that are specific to Nansat should contain clear identifier	1	Finished
Strip down Nansat	2	Finished
Check CF-compliance of test files	2	Finished
Assert overlap of source and destination domains for reprojection	2	Finished
Docs in ReadTheDocs style/format	89	Finished
Replace wiki pages on GitHub by a web page (ghpages) and ReadTheDocs	5	Finished
Sentinel-1 problem of reshaping geolocation grids	1	Finished
Interpolation problem on converting LUT values into full resolution image grid?	1	Finished
Reduce number of branches	3	Finished
Refactor and clean up the Nansat package	89	Finished
Integration with Anaconda	13	Not finished
Configure virtual machine environment and travisCI to Python 3	1	Not finished
Split functionality in generic mapper	55	Not finished
GeoTIFF mapper reads GCPProjection from metadata only	2	Not finished
OPeNDAP mapper should be updated and activated	8	Not finished
Possible bug with Domain from dataset with polar stereographic projection	2	Not finished
Fast reproject	3	Not finished
Nansat.crop should recreate GCPs from geolocation array	3	Not finished
Add option to validate metadata	5	Not finished

*External blocker with unusually slow response from conda-forge slowed down the completion of this task. The task was completed shortly after the sprint as the conda-forge team finally accepted Nansat as a feedstock.

The cards and points distribution per tag indicates that highest priority has been put on severe tags, then in ascending order bugs, enhancements and questions. Each card can have multiple tags.

Tag	# of Cards	Cards Finished	Points	Points Finished	% Points Finished
severe	1	1	13	13	100
bug	8	4	206	192	93.2038835
enhancement	14	9	293	214	73.03754266
question	4	1	17	5	29.41176471

Sprint Planning

Sprint Planning Date: 2018-01-09 to 2018-01-10

Sprint Planning Participants: All team members

During the planning meeting, the sprint process was briefly explained to the team, and the team started evaluating each card in the backlog. This took longer than expected and had to continue the next day. The task of finishing creating and defining subtasks as per discussion were distributed among the team, to be done shortly after the meeting.

The Sprint Goal was defined as: “Modernise and improve visibility and competitiveness of Nansat.” This is what the team should have in mind during the entire sprint.

A “Definition of Done” (DoD) was agreed upon. This is a list of tasks that need to be done before each card can be considered complete. The DoD consists of the following bullet points:

- Tests are passing
- 100% test coverage on new code
- There should be no overlapping/obsolete branches overlapping the issue at hand.
- Follow PEP-8
- New code should be Python 3 compatible.
- Line length of max 100 characters
- All names should be explicit
- Follow Nansat conventions. These were updated by Artem shortly after the meeting.

Sprint Review

Sprint Review Date: 2018-01-26

Sprint Review Participants: All team members and Asle Steiestøl Wingsternes

The progress and results of all cards were presented by those who had worked on them. All completed tasks were accepted by the Product Owner.

The team agreed that the daily scrums were very useful and efficient.

The team and the product owner were satisfied with the completed tasks, and it was stated that the sprint goal was achieved.

Sprint Retrospective

Sprint Retrospective Date: 2018-02-08

Sprint Retrospective Participants: M. Hansen, A. Korosov, T. Olaussen and A. Vines

The main conclusion about the sprint was that there were too many bugs in the released code. This was discovered during the weeks after the sprint. One therefore needs to be more thorough when writing tests and reviewing other's code. One of the tasks included a major rewrite of large parts of Nansat. This should probably have been split up, although it was difficult as long as the different parts of Nansat were very tightly coupled¹. Therefore, development of Nansat should strive to make it more loosely coupled in the future. As a side-note, it did also get more loosely coupled during the sprint.

To better follow the work progress, work-hours should be filled in on each subtask next time. This will lead to a more meaningful burn down chart and can help to measure the performance during the sprint. A good understanding of the performance could help in estimating development time needed in future sprints, also helping to keep the time schedule.

During the sprint planning, a lot of time was spent on analysing the cards in plenum. Some of this work, especially identifying subtasks, could have been done in advance by the Product Owner, or distributed and done individually. Hence, the sprint planning would be more efficient. Also, the Scrum Master had not informed the Product Owner that he should present and take full ownership of the cards in the backlog. This could easily be improved in future sprints.

Other

The release of Nansat 1.0 was advertised in Nansen News 2/2018 and in social media (see <https://mailchi.mp/ebe66bd6d4c8/nansen-news-22018>).

¹ Robert C. Martin, (2002) *Agile Software Development, Principles, Patterns, and Practices*. ISBN-10: 0-13-597444-5